

ISic3459

Inscription recording building work by Publius Stertinius Threptus

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone (?)

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Excavated July 2010, in re-use on the decumanus maximus, Capo Boeo

Coordinates

37.803041, 12.428914

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 174 cm

Width 65-66 cm

Depth 13-15 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 80 mm

Line 2: 75 mm

Line 3: 65 mm

Lines 4-5: 70 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: Not measured mm

Text

1. P (ublius) Stertinius Threptus
3. plateam platiam Aeliam
4. sua pecunia
5. stravit

Apparatus

Text of Silvestrini 2014

Translation (en)

Publius Stertinius Threptus paved the Platea Aelia with his own money

Commentary

Silvestrini proposes that the name of the platea (a wide street, not a square,

and so very probably the decumanus maximus) should be linked to the visit of the Emperor Hadrian in 125 AD. Naming of streets after an emperor in this fashion finds parallels. Other instances of platea inscriptions are known in Sicily (AE 1964.181 and AE 1964.182 both from Marsala; and AE 1997.740 from Segesta). The name implies a freedman (Silvestrini notes the significant family of Stertini from the early C2 AD, and that perhaps they have a Sicilian origin on the basis of this text; at 223 n.63 Silvestrini speculates a link with the recently found Isis dedication from Lilybaeum (noted in Silvestrini (2011) 464 n.6), by a Rufinius, which could be cos. of 162, D. Fonteius Frontinianus L. Stertinus Rufinus.

Digital identifiers:

TM 644936

Bibliography

Silvestrini, M. 2014. Nuove epigrafi da Lilibeo. In Zaccaria, C.(eds.), *L'Epigrafia dei porti. Atti della XVIIe rencontre sur l'épigraphie du monde romain, Aquileia, 14-16 ottobre 2010*. Trieste. pp. 207-226. At 220-223 no.4 fig.11

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